

CONCEPT STUDY FOR THE MATERIAL COMPLIANT IMPLEMENTATION OF THE RFID TECHNOLOGY INTO CARBON FIBRE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Radio-frequency identification (RFID), a technology for transmitter-receiver systems in order to automatically and contactlessly identify and locate objects using electromagnetic fields or waves, is a versatile technology for wireless power transmission and storage and structural health monitoring in multifunctional composite materials. A new approach regarding the material compliant implementation of the major RFID components into carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) structures is presented.

It was focused on the development of material compliant antenna coils and capacitors made of CFRP. Transponder coils were made of nickel-coated and uncoated carbon fibre yarn. For the capacitor an electrochemical double layer capacitor with carbon fibre electrodes and lithium ions was developed. To assess the suitability of CFRP as coil material for the RFID technology experiments were carried out with a copper coil for comparison. Measurements were established in which frequencies from 100 kHz to 140 kHz were applied in order to determine the inductance and the resistance. For the CFRP capacitor the capacitance as well as the loading and unloading behavior were the main analyzed criteria. To gain information about the possibility of using CFRP coils for energy transmission, the manufactured coils were extended to resonant circuits with a predetermined resonance frequency of 122 kHz. The behavior of the resonant circuit was simulated and verified by means of a LTspice IV simulation. It has been found out, that in spite of a much higher electrical resistance of the uncoated fibre material, still an effective power between 4.6 mW and 170 mW was transmitted through inductive coupling. Regarding the capacitance of the CFRP capacitors values of 50 nF were recorded. Using the much higher resistance of the uncoated carbon fibre material as an advantage, the resonant circuit made out of CFRP components is predestined as a sensor system to monitor structural damages of CFRP parts wirelessly.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) are seen as a material of high potential, especially in the area of the automotive industry. New vehicle concepts like the BMW i3 demonstrate, that composite materials offer advanced design possibilities, reduce time to market and improve flexibilities in medium series productions.

Radio-frequency identification (RFID), a technology for transmitter-receiver systems in order to automatically and contactlessly identify and locate objects by using electromagnetic fields is an established technology in many fields of the automotive industry. By the use of the RFID technology in combination with vehicle parts made out of carbon fibre, not only the simplified and complete documentation of a component, from manufacturing of an automobile to later customer service is possible, but also the energy coupling into the material via the wireless RFID technology will be a promising option for further application regarding the automotive industry. One area of application for this approach might be effective health monitoring systems.

A concept study regarding the feasibility of the implementation of the radio frequency technology into carbon fibre material was investigated. Technical approaches and methods have been developed

to achieve the implementation of the RFID technology into carbon fibre material regarding material compatibility.

Referring to the applications (identification and monitoring) an operating frequency in the range up to 150 kHz (low frequency) for a close-coupling system (distance up to 3 cm) was defined [1,2].

Carbon fibre is a conductive material and represents for this reason a special challenge for the implementation of the transponder into the material. In order to achieve a material compliant implementation, first, the main components of an RFID system (coil and capacitor) were analysed. A simple RFID system without semiconductor chip, according to the requirements by the implementation in CFRP, was designed and manufactured under consideration of the advantages and disadvantages.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 CFRP-Coil

A RFID system is typically made up of two components: the transponder or tag and the data acquisition device often referred to as reader or transceiver [1,2]. The tag is generally physically attached to an object or integrated into the product. Inductive coupling is used at low frequency RFID systems operating in the near field. Therefore, the reader transmits energy to the passive tag at frequencies between 125 - 135 kHz, see Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Schematic structure of an inductive coupling system [3]

The efficiency of the energy transfer between sender and receiver can be expressed as [1,2]:

$$\eta_{max} = \frac{\Delta}{(1 + \sqrt{1 + \Delta})^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta = K_{12}^2 Q_1 Q_2$$

Both transponder and reader have to be tuned at the same resonance frequency to achieve a high energy transfer. According to the resonant frequency f_0 of both circuits can be determined:

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_R C_R}} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_T C_T}} \quad (2)$$

Using a CFRP coil antenna for the material compliant implementation of a RFID tag, would not interfere with the structure in contrast to a standard metal antenna. But the carbon fibre material degrades the wireless performance due to its conductivity, especially when placed on CFRP background material.

With respect to the shape of the antenna, there is a variety of opportunities. In the design of the antenna geometry and shape, basically no limits are set. For the first estimate on the geometry of a flat coil the contour of a spiral of Archimedes was chosen. For a given outer diameter D_0 , an inner

diameter D_I , conductor diameter D_D and conductor pitch D_P the resulting inductance L_C can be approximated as followed [4]:

$$L_C = \frac{\left[\frac{D_I + (D_P + D_C)n}{2} \right]^2 n^2}{8 \left[\frac{D_I + (D_P + D_C)n}{2} \right] + 11(D_P + D_C)n} \quad (3)$$

For considering fibre material as an adequate replacement for copper wire regarding the manufacture of RFID coils, the coil quality is an important value. The quality factor of a coil Q_L in general is a dimensionless value for the losses due to the ohmic losses of the coil wire. The losses behave inversely proportional to the coil quality. The quality factor is calculated as the ratio of the reactance X_L and the effective resistance R_L of a coil. It influences the properties of a resonant circuit in particular in the vicinity of the resonance frequency. Generally the quality factor depends on frequency due to skin and proximity effect.

$$Q_L = \frac{X_L}{R_L} = \frac{\omega_0 L}{R_L} \quad (4)$$

2.1 CFRP-Capacitor

In addition to the coil a capacitor is required to form a resonance circuit for RFID. The work concentrates on the application of structural CRFP based capacitors as demonstrated by Snyder, Carlson et al. [8-12]. A schematic description of the double layer capacitor is given in Fig.2. The approach is based on the high reversible capacity of carbon fibres, which are used as electrodes. The electrodes are separated by a layer (separator), which is ionically conducting but electronically insulating. A structural polymer electrolyte and lithium ions are used as charge carriers. The thin carbon filaments ($7\mu\text{m}$) provide a large electrode surface area to accumulate lithium ions. Typically for this capacitor type the voltage difference between the two electrodes is limited to a few volts.

Figure 2: Schematic description of the structural composite capacitor

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 CFRP coil antenna

The nickel coated carbon fibre yarn Tenax HTS 40 A23 12K and the uncoated carbon fibre Toray T300, 1K were selected as fibre materials for the antenna coils. The uncoated fibre used has only 1.000 filaments compared to the nickel coated carbon fibre, which had 12,000 filaments. To get the

same number of filaments and more importantly the same conductor diameter of the coil, the fibre roving was set 12 times, twisted and then inserted into the coil mould. Tab. 1 gives an overview over the manufactured coils.

Antenna Coil	Fibre	Diameter	Turns
CFRP coil (T300)	T300 1k (*12)	78 mm	19
CFRP-Nickel coil	HTS 40	82 mm	20
Cooper coil	1 mm	“	“

Table 1: Manufactured coils

To form the carbon reinforced fibre yarn into the shape of an Archimedean spiral a negative mould was constructed. As a material for this purpose Polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE) has been chosen, in order to avoid bonding of the cured material. PTFE has an extremely low surface tension therefore provides the best properties to demould the impregnated coil without damaging it.

The roving was impregnated by means of an injection needle with 2.0 ml/m epoxy resin adhesive and then cured at 180° C for 3 hours. The used epoxy resin adhesive (HBM EP310S) has a very low viscosity hence it is able to penetrate the individual filaments of the fibre roving through the capillarity.

According to equation 3 the inductance of the antenna coil with an outer diameter of 82 mm, no inner diameter and a yarn diameter of 1 mm is determined to 11.423 μ H (20 turns).

Figure 3: Manufacturing of the CFRP-antenna

A plastic coated wire with a diameter of 1 mm was used as a spacer between the turns of the coil after demoulding in order to achieve constant distances. The coils were placed on a transparent, one sided adhesive tape (Nopi). Then the coated wire was formed and placed section by section from the inside to the outside of the coil between the CFRP coil turns. To eliminate possible effects of the spacer wire used on the measurement results the spacer was removed. In the end the final result of the coil was coated with a second layer of the transparent adhesive tape in order to keep it in shape.

After that the electrical connection was performed, the vertical bars in the centre and at the outermost turn of the coil were flamed, nickel-plated and then coated with solder [13, 14].

For comparison reasons an almost identical copper coil compared to the CFRP coils was manufactured. The material used to bend the coil was enamelled (electrical isolated) copper wire, in order to prevent shortcuts caused by possibly touching coil turns. The copper coil had an outside diameter of 82 mm, with 20 turns, distance from turn to turn of 1.0 mm and no inner diameter. The wire diameter was selected as 1 mm, to easily fit into the 1.0 mm wide groove of the antenna coil mould.

Material	Relative permeability μ_r	Resistivity ρ	Thickness
Plastics (Reference Air)	≈ 1	$> 1 \times 10^8 \frac{\Omega \text{mm}^2}{m}$	3 mm
Aluminium	1.00002	$2.65 \times 10^{-2} \frac{\Omega \text{mm}^2}{m}$	4 and 10 mm
CFRP (quasi-isotropic T300/913)	≈ 1	$20 \text{ to } 1 \times 10^3 \frac{\Omega \text{mm}^2}{m}$	3 mm
Inconel 625	1.0006	$1.29 \frac{\Omega \text{mm}^2}{m}$	3 mm

Table 2: Overview of the different carrier materials used to study the influence of the surrounding material on the signal

Different measurements were established to characterize the behavior of the antenna coils. Frequencies from 100 kHz to 140 kHz were applied in order to determine the inductance and the resistance (LCR-8110G, Instek). Aluminium, Inconel and CFRP plates were applied to measure the influence of the surrounding material on the transponder coil (Tab.2).

The manufactured coils were extended by suitable capacitors to resonant circuits with a constant resonance frequency of 122 kHz. The behavior of the resonant circuit was measured and verified by means of a LTspice IV simulation (Fig. 4 and 5). The voltages and the currents of the transmitting coil and of the receiver coils were measured to determine the possible energy transmission.

Figure 4: Experimental set-up for the coupling of the two coils

Figure 5: Simulation model for coupling experiment as used in the set-up

3.2 Capacitor

The double layer capacitor consists of 6 carbon layers (SGL 300 gr/m²) of a non-crimp fabric having the lay-up $[0,0,0]_{\text{sym}}$. In the symmetry the separator (Celgard 2500) was arranged. The size of the capacitor was 100*100 mm. The electrical connection was performed by means of two copper meshes (100*50mm), which were arranged in the middle of the outer layers. Lithium trifluoromethanesulfonate (Sigma Aldrich) was dissolved in polyethylene glycol 200 (PEG, Sigma Aldrich). As resin a vinylester (Odopal A 430-01-TV, BÜFA GmbH) with a MEKP hardener was applied to obtain a one molar solution of lithium and PEG [8]. In a prestudy the influence of the amount of PEG on the conductivity of the neat resin was investigated.

To evaluate the electrical performance of the CFRP capacitor the capacity and the resistance were characterized in the range of 0.01 to 1000 kHz (LCR-8110G, Instek), which is the range of interest for RFID. Furthermore the loading and unloading behavior for resonance frequencies and different circuit arrangements were tested. The mechanical performance of the structural capacitor was assessed by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and the determination of the interlaminar fracture toughness (AITM 1.0005).

Figure 6: CFRP capacitor size 100*100 mm

4 RESULTS

4.1 Antenna coil inductance and resistance

Figs. 7 to 9 show the measured resistances and inductances versus the frequency for all coils investigated.

Figure 7: Resistance and inductance vs. frequency for the cooper coil

Figure 8: Resistance and inductance vs. frequency for the CFRP-Nickel coil

Figure 9: Resistance and inductance vs. frequency for the CFRP coil

It could be noted that identical coils out of different materials differ only significantly in resistance but not in the inductance. Furthermore, the inductance of the coil was reduced, in particular at high frequencies, especially when placed on CFRP as background material (factor 3 to 10) because of the shielding effect of eddy currents in conductive materials and the limited frequency dependent depth of penetration of the magnetic field. The nickel coated carbon fibre material showed a much lower resistance (10Ω compared to 80Ω) even at low frequencies than the uncoated carbon fibre. During the use of flat spiral coils out of CFRP as antennas, inductances of $11.3 \mu\text{H}$ and $11.4 \mu\text{H}$ were achieved. The increase of the resistance at high frequencies can be attributed to skin effects. This is not the case for the nickel coated carbon fibre. The thin nickel coating ($0,25\mu\text{m}$) forms already a thin layer of high conductivity resulting in elevated current density in the outer layer.

Fig. 10 shows the course of the coil quality factor versus the frequency measured for the nickel coated carbon fibre coil and the copper coil. The quality factor of the copper coil is many times higher than the one of the nickel coated carbon fibre coil ($60\times$ at 105 kHz). This can be explained by the fact that the resistance of the nickel coated carbon fibre is much higher compared to copper.

Figure 10: Quality factor of the CFRP-Nickel coil (left) and the copper coil (right) vs. frequency

4.2 Coupling of two coils

All results which are shown in this section depend on the coupling factor between sender coil and receiver coil and the magnetic field of the sender. In order to compare the receiver coils the experimental parameters were kept constant during the measurements.

Fig. 11 depicts the voltage in the CFRP-Ni coil. The expected maximum of the voltage is in the area of the resonant frequency of the resonant circuit. There was no significant difference in the voltage profile over the frequency detected, when measuring in air or on a CFRP plate. The maximum voltage in air was 4.79 V and when placing the CFRP-Ni coil on carbon 4.37 V. This equals a voltage reduction of 8.77 % due to the use of CFRP as a background material compared to the measurement in air.

Fig.11: Receiver voltage, current and effective power vs. frequency for the CFRP-Nickel coil

The graphs of the current in the coupled CFRP-Ni coil showed similarity with those of the voltage. The maximum of the curve was again, in the region of the resonant frequency at 0.547 A and when placing the coil on carbon fibre it decreased to 0.505 A. This equals a current reduction of 7.68 % due to the use of CFRP as background material. For the consideration of the CFRP-Nickel coil as a potential replacement for a regularly used copper coil within the RFID technology, the effective power of the transponder coil was of interest. The measured curve in air and with carbon fibre as background material is shown in Fig. 11. It can be seen clearly that the use of carbon fibre as substrate has a strong influence on the effective power. The effective power of the CFRP-Nickel coil when measured in air was noted at 0.17 W, whereas the effective power was only 0.0804 W after placing the nickel-coated CFRP coil on a carbon fibre plate. This represents a decrease regarding the effective power of 52.7 %. Tab. 3 shows the results for all antenna coils and background materials investigated.

Coil material / background	I	U	P
CFRP-Nickel / Air	0,547 A	4,8 V	0,170 W
CFRP-Nickel / CFRP	0,505 A	4,4 V	0,0804 W
CFRP / Air	0,02 A	2V	0,031 W
CFRP / CFRP	0,024 A	2V	0,033 W
Copper / Air	3,7 A	32,4V	1,5 W
Copper / CFRP	2,1 A	18,5 V	0,273 W

Table 3: Overview of the absolute values (U, I, P) of the receiver coils with different background materials

Tab. 4 shows the transmitted values in the respective receiver coils as a percentage of the values in the transmitting coil with respect to the coil current I, the coil voltage U and the effective power P.

Coil material / background	ΔI	ΔU	ΔP
CFRP-Nickel / Air	12,9 %	0,50 %	1,21 %
CFRP-Nickel / CFRP	12,1 %	0,47 %	0,58 %
CFRP / Air	0,36 %	0,12 %	0,03 %
CFRP / CFRP	0,41 %	0,23 %	0,14 %
Copper / Air	145 %	5,66 %	16,80 %
Copper / CFRP	65 %	2,60 %	2,57 %

Table 4: Transferred energy (ΔU , ΔI and ΔP) from transmitter to receiver coil in percent

It has been found out, that in spite of a much higher electrical resistance of the uncoated carbon fibre, still sufficient effective power from the inductive coupling was available in order to supply a

possible transponder chip by the resonant circuit of the receiver. A low power chip needs an electrical power of 10 μ W. The voltage induced in the receiver coil, which acts as an antenna, supplies the chip with sufficient power. Between the chip and the coil is a rectifier with limited efficiency. This means, that the antenna must receive at least approximately 50 μ W in order to qualify for the energy transfer using the RFID technology. The values of the effective power obtained in the experiment of the two CFRP coils at resonance were above this limit.

4.3 Capacitor

Fig. 12 shows the influence of the PEG content on the electrical conductivity of the neat resin. It can be seen that a conductivity of nearly 1×10^{-4} S/cm can be achieved for a PEG-concentration of 40 % vol. For higher PEG concentrations only a low increase of the conductivity was found. Therefore a PEG-concentration of 40 % vol. related to the neat resin was selected.

Figure 12: Influence of the PEG200 content on the conductivity of the neat resin

Fig. 13 shows the electrical resistance and the capacity of the CFRP-capacitor (100*100 mm) versus the frequency. For the frequency range investigated (0.01 to 1000 kHz) the resistance shows a decrease from 100 to 10 Ohm. The influence of the frequency on the capacity is high. At 0,01 kHz a capacity of 500 μ F was measured and at 1000 Hz a capacity of 0,1 μ F. This strong influence of the frequency on the capacitor can be attributed to the transport of lithium ions during charge and discharge. At higher frequencies the duration for the transport of ions becomes smaller. For the frequency range applied for conventional RFID applications a capacity of about 1 to 0.5 μ F can be achieved. The investigation showed that double layer capacitors can be realized by means of lithium ions as charge carrier collected at high surface area of carbon fibre electrodes.

Figure 13: Behaviour of the structural CFRP-capacitor

5 OUTLOOK

The combination of a transponder coil and a capacitor out of carbon fibres form a resonant circuit for RFID technique. Based on this approach data can be transferred wirelessly by means of electromagnetic fields. In [14] it has been demonstrated that carbon fibres can be used as sensor element to measure strain levels and to detect damages, like micro-cracks and delaminations. Fig. 14 shows a new RFID device, a double layer capacitor with transponder coil and a carbon fibre sensor element. The electrical resistance and inductivity of the carbon fibre sensor element is influenced by damages of the carbon structure, which will cause a shift of the resonance frequency of the RFID device. Therefore this device can be applied for the wireless health monitoring of CFRP structures.

Figure 14: RFID device out of CFRP, electrochemical double layer capacitor with transponder coil and a carbon fibre sensor element

6 CONCLUSIONS

Identical coils made out of different materials (carbon fibres, nickel coated carbon fibres and copper) differ only significantly in resistance, but not in the inductance. Furthermore, the inductance of the coils was reduced, in particular at high frequencies, especially when placed on CFRP as background material.

By coupling the secondary resonant circuit to a primary resonant circuit with an inductance of 297 μH and an applied voltage of 8 V an effective power between 4.6 mW and 170 mW could be noted due to resonant peak. Commercially available low-power chips require a power of 50 μW , taking into account the loss of a required rectifier. The use of carbon fibres for the manufacturing of the transponder coil as antenna for a possible use in the field of radio frequency was proven to be very promising.

In addition to the CFRP-coil a structural CRFP-based double-layer capacitor was designed and manufactured. The capacitor (6 carbon layers, 100 x 100 mm) exhibits a capacity of about 1 to 0.5 μF and a resistance of 50 Ω for the frequency range used for conventional RFID applications. The combination of antennas and capacitors out of carbon fibres form a resonant circuit. In combination with a carbon fibre sensor element the system has a high potential for a wireless health monitoring system for CFRP structures.

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